

INTERFACE FEATURES OF THE C/C COMPOSITE DURING ITS FORMING PROCESS WITH A COAL-TAR-PITCH AS THE PRECURSOR OF THE CARBON MATRIX

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Keywords: C/C composite, Interface feature, coal-tar-pitch, interface strength

ABSTRACT

The forming of the C/C composite usually includes many repetitive processes of impregnating, carbonization and heat-treatment at high temperatures when the coal-tar-pitch is used as the precursor of the carbon matrix. For the validity of densification, the impregnating process is applied at high pressures and at high temperatures. In this work, the interface features of the C/C composite during its forming process were studied systematically. It has been found that the interface feature of the fiber/matrix in the fiber bundles formed in the initial stage and the fiber/matrix interfaces between the fiber bundles formed throughout the forming process of the C/C composite. With the increase of the density of the C/C composite, the interface strength (IS) tended to increase. The IS of the fiber/matrix in the fiber bundles is much higher than that between the fiber bundles. The temperature of the heat-treatment (HTT) is a key factor to influence the interface strength. Higher HTT will decrease the interface strength due to the forming of the micro-cracks at the interfaces. The interface features could be controlled by the HTT.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon/carbon composite (C/C composite) has been used as the thermal protection material (TPM) of many high-speed aircrafts due to its high mechanical performance and high dimensional stability at high temperatures [1,2]. During the preparation process of C/C composites, hydrocarbons, resins and pitches are usually used as the precursors of the carbon matrix. For the TPMs that work at super high temperatures (specially above 2000°C), high density C/C composites are needed to increase the ablation performance by decreasing the surface recession rate [3,4]. The densification technique of impregnating/carbonization with pitch as the precursors of the carbon matrix is adopted to form C/C composites under high pressures. During this process, impregnating, carbonization and heat-treatment at high temperatures proceed alternately [1,2].

In this work, interface features of the C/C composite during its densification process with a coal-tar-pitch as the precursor of the carbon matrix were studied. The interface strengths (IS) of fiber/carbon matrix in and between the fiber bundles were analyzed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL MATERIALS AND PROCEDURES

2.1 Preparation of C/C composite

In this paper, a C/C composite was prepared from a three-dimensional orthogonal woven fabric with a coal tar pitch as the precursor of the carbon matrix. The repetitive impregnating, carbonization and heat-treatment at high temperatures (HTT) were used to densify the preform. In Fig.1, the compendary process of the C/C composite forming is shown.

During the preparation, five carbonizations at usual pressure and four carbonizations at high pressure above 30MPa were used. The carbonization temperature is 900°C. After carbonization except for the first one, HTT at the temperatures of 1500~2300°C was used to promote the carbonization deeply. After each carbonization and HTT, the C/C composite was sampled for analysis.

Fig.1 Preparation process of C/C composite

2.2 Analysis

2.2.1 Microstructure observation

The C/C composites at different stages were sampled and then used to obtain the observation samples for metallographic analysis. The small C/C composite samples were firstly embedded in an epoxy-resin to form cylindrical blocks and then polished with sand papers and polishing clothes. The obtained samples were observed under a polarized optical microscope (Leica, DM2500P). The regions between the fiber bundles and in the fiber bundles were focused.

To make clear of the interface features of the single fibers, TEM observation was conducted on the samples that were thinned by ion milling and the interface junctions were focused.

2.2.2 Interface strength test

The interface strength was tested with the push-out method. Before test, a thin C/C composite flake was cut and then polished. The fiber bundles and their fibers should be vertical to the test surface. During the test, the test needle pushes the fiber bundle or a single fiber out and the force was recorded. The process of push-out test of a fiber bundle or a single fiber is given in Fig.2. The interface strength was calculated using the following equation. To obtain the data that is meaningful, at least ten data were averaged for each test.

$\tau = f / lh$, Here, f is the maximum force. h is the thickness of the test samples or the length of the fiber bundles or single fibers. l is the perimeter of the fiber bundles or single fibers.

Fig.2 The process of push-out test of fiber bundle or single fiber

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Changes of the bulk density of the C/C composite

During the forming of the C/C composite, the carbon fiber perform is densified gradually. Fig.2 gives the process of the density. It can be seen from Fig.2 that the bulk density increases while the densification cycle goes on as a whole. After each heat-treatment (HT), the density has a small decrease due to the deeper carbonization of the carbon matrix. During the carbonization at usual pressure, the increment tends to reduce. The bulk density has a great increase when the carbonization was firstly carried out at high pressure above 30MPa, although it has still small increment during the

next carbonation.

Fig.2 Density of the C/C composite during different process

3.2 Evolution of the interface morphology

In the C/C composite, there are two interfaces including the one between the fiber bundles and the other in the fiber bundles. The former one is formed by the fiber bundles and the carbon matrix and the latter one come into being by the single fibers and the carbon matrix around them. The interface morphologies of the cross-sections of the C/C composite during different processes are shown in Fig.3-Fig.8.

It can be seen from Fig.3 that after the first carbonization (1C) few of carbon matrix can form between the fiber bundles and large holes and crack still exist. In the fiber bundles, almost all the pores were filled by the carbon matrix although some small ones and some microcracks are left. After the first HT (1H), the interface morphologies show similar to that of 1C, but the ones in the fiber bundles more pores and microcracks can be observed.

Fig.3 Polarized optical micrographs of the cross-sections of the C/C composite in the first densification cycle

After the third carbonization (3C) of the second densification cycle, more carbon matrix can be found in the small cracks between the fiber bundles and the small pores and microcracks in the fiber bundles were filled by the carbon matrix as shown in Fig.4. The large holes and cracks are still lack of carbon matrix. After the second HT (2H), more cracks and microcracks appeared at the interfaces between and in the fiber bundles. Few of carbon matrixes formed in the large holes and large cracks.

Fig.4 Polarized optical micrographs of the cross-sections of the C/C composite in the second densification cycle

After the third densification cycle, more carbon matrixes are filled in the small cracks and holes and microcracks still exist after the HT as shown in Fig.5. Although more one densification cycle was carried out, the cross-sections in Fig.6 shows the similar features to that in Fig.5 except that the cracks and holes become smaller.

The cross-sections of the C/C composites sampled after the fifth densification are shown in Fig.7. It can be seen from Fig.7 that lots of carbon matrixes were filled in the large holes and cracks between the fiber bundles after the first carbonization at high pressure (1P). On the cross-sections of the sample after the HT (5H), more cracks formed around the fiber bundles and few of microcracks can be found in the fiber bundles.

With the densification cycles increasing, the holes and cracks were stuffed by the carbon matrix, but small cracks will still form around the fiber bundles after the followed HT. Almost no microcracks can be found in the fiber bundles during the following densification cycles. After eighth densification cycle, i.e. four carbonization at high pressure and four HTs, the cracks still exist around the fiber bundles as given in Fig.8.

Fig.5 Polarized optical micrographs of the cross-sections of the C/C composite in the third densification cycle

Fig.6 Polarized optical micrographs of the cross-sections of the C/C composite in the fourth densification cycle

Fig.7 Polarized optical micrographs of the cross-sections of the C/C composite in the fifth densification cycle

Fig.8 Polarized optical micrographs of the cross-sections of the C/C composite in the eighth densification cycle

3.3 Evolution of the interface strength

The interface strengths of the fiber bundles (ISFB) during the densification cycles are given in Fig.9. It can be seen that during the carbonization the ISFB increases. After the second carbonization at usual pressure and after the first carbonization at high pressure, the ISFB has a great increase. After the HT, the ISFB tends to become small. When the HT carried out at higher temperatures, the ISFB has a large decrease, for example the ISFB after 5H. With the densification proceeds, the ISFB increases gradually even HT was applied after carbonization taking no account of the HT at higher temperatures.

Fig.9 Interface strength of the fiber bundles during the impregnating/carbonation (black circle) and the high temperature heat-treatment (red star)

In Fig.10, the interface strengths of the single fibers (ISSF) during the densification cycles are given. It can be seen that the ISSF falls in the range of 15MPa -22MPa for the carbonized samples, although the densification cycle increases as shown in Fig.10. For the heat-treated samples at high temperatures that followed after the carbonization at usual pressure, the ISSF is similar to the ISFB as given above, but the ISSF tend to decrease to a large degree. With the increase of densification cycle, the ISSF increases and then decreases when the HT was carried out at a higher temperature. It is very interesting that, during the densification process at high pressure, the ISSF increases continuously in spite of the existing of HT after each carbonization.

Fig.10 Interface strength of the single fibers during the impregnating/carbonation (black circle) and the high temperature heat-treatment (red star)

3.4 Discussions

With the increase of the densification cycle, the carbon matrix formed both in and among the fiber bundles. At the initial stages, densification was carried out at usual pressure and the carbon matrix tends to form in the fiber bundles. Due to the lack of carbon matrix, the ISFB is very low at the first densification cycle and then increases with the repeating of the impregnating/carbonization/HT. With the high filling ratio in the fiber bundles, the ISSF is much higher than ISFB, although the value is still low. The HT process promotes the deeper carbonization of carbon matrix and cause many cracks or microcracks at the interfaces of both single fibers and fiber bundles, which decreases the interface strength. Higher HTT will form larger cracks or microcracks and then cause a decrease of interface strength to a larger degree. For the preferential filling of carbon matrix in the fiber bundles, the interface of single fibers/carbon matrix forms firstly and its interface strength has no obvious increase during the carbonization at usual pressure even if the densification cycle goes on.

Fig.11 shows the TEM micrographs of the interface region of single fiber/matrix in C/C composite. It can be seen that the carbon fiber has a strong connection through the forming of the bridge-bonds of carbon layers, which is the reason that ISSF is much higher than ISFB.

Fig.11 TEM micrographs of the interface region of carbon fiber/matrix in C/C composite

During the densification process at high pressure, there is no obvious filling of carbon matrix in the fiber bundles for the previous densification. The carbon matrix was filled basically in the microcracks that were formed during the near former HT. The ISSF has little increases after carbonization but has a large one after HT compared to the previous cycle due to the forming of more bridge-bonds of carbon layers at the interface of carbon fibers and carbon matrix. The ISFB has a large increase after the impregnating/carbonization at high pressure due to the effective filling of carbon matrix among the fiber bundles. However, the forming of large cracks around the fiber bundles after the HT still reduced the ISFB greatly.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The interface morphologies and interface strengths were systematically analyzed during the forming of a C/C composite forming. It has been found that the interface of the fiber/carbon matrix in the fiber bundles formed in the initial stages and that between the fiber bundles formed throughout the forming process of the C/C composite.

The interface strength is related to the interface status that was controlled by the heat-treatment. For the ISFB, it increases with the densification cycle increasing if carbonation is only considered. HT can decrease the ISFB, especially when the HT was carried out at higher temperatures.

The ISSF is higher than the ISFB for the closed connection between the fiber and the carbon matrix and the fast filling of carbon matrix in the fiber bundles. For the carbonization at usual pressure, the ISSF has small increase although the densification cycle goes on and the HT next to the carbonization can also decrease it. For the carbonization at high pressure, the ISSF increases with the densification cycle. The HT next to the carbonization can form many bridge-bonds and then increase s the ISSF.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The present work was financially supported by the National Basic Research Program of China (973 Program) (2011CB605802) and the Science Foundation of Science and Technology on Advanced Functional Composites Laboratory (9140C560109130C569199).

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